

Self-assessment Tool for Teachers When Designing OER-Only Blended Learning

Alvarez, L., Correia, J., Berset, L., Ramillon, C., & Bugmann, J. (2025)

INSTRUCTIONS FOR THE SELF-ASSESSMENT. Remember that self-assessment is an ongoing process. Regularly reflect on your teaching practices thanks to the listed questions below, to ensure continuous growth and improvement in designing effective OER-only blended learning experiences for your students.

Section A: Planning and Preparation Instruction (8 points)

A1. Have I clearly defined the learning objectives and outcomes for my students?

- Yes, I have well-defined learning objectives (2 points).
- Somewhat, but could improve clarity (1 point).
- No, need to revisit learning objectives (0 point).

A2. Have I clearly defined the targeted audience and their needs, including any potential biases or barriers?

- Yes, I have well-defined the targeted audience (2 points).
- Somewhat, but could improve clarity (1 point).
- No, need to revisit the clarification of the targeted audience (0 point).

A3. Am I fully qualified and confident for OER-only blended learning design, thanks to professional development or other forms of training?

- Yes, I attended related professional development or other forms of training (2 points).
- Somewhat, but could improve develop my skill by attending professional development (1 point).
- No, need to fully engage in professional development (0 point).

A4. Have I established a network of partners (e.g., librarian, IT, other teachers, instructional designer) to ensure that I have all the necessary skills to design OER-only blended learning?

- Yes, I am well supported by the necessary partners (2 points).
- Somewhat, but should seek some specialist help (1 point).
- No, need to build a network of partners from scratch (0 point).

Section B: Blending Instructional Strategies (14 points)

B1. Have I identified the most effective blend of online and face-to-face instruction for this course/content?

- Yes, my blended approach is well suited for this content (2 points).
- Somewhat, but could explore alternative blends (1 point).
- No, need to rethink my blended design (0 point).

B2. Have I used a variety of digital tools and resources both in online and face-to-face instruction, that align with the learning objectives?

- Yes, I have a range of relevant digital tools and resources (2 points).
- Somewhat, but could add more diversity (1 point).
- No, need to explore new digital options (0 point).

B3. Are my instructional strategies flexible enough to accommodate different learning styles and needs?

- Yes, I have a range of adaptable strategies (2 points).
- Somewhat, but could improve flexibility (1 point).
- No, need to develop more inclusive approaches (0 point).

B4. Am I using instructional strategies to facilitate active learning experiences for students?

- Yes, my online activities promote student engagement and participation (2 points).
- Somewhat, but could enhance interactivity (1 point).
- No, need to rethink online activities (0 point).

B5. Are my face-to-face interactions with students focused on building relationships, providing feedback, and facilitating discussions?

- Yes, I prioritize meaningful connections for the in-person moments (2 points).
- Somewhat, but could improve the balance between tech and human interaction (1 point).
- No, need to rethink face-to-face interactions (0 point).

B6. Have I developed assessments that align with my learning objectives and blend of online and face-to-face instruction?

- Yes, my assessments are well suited for this blended course (2 points).
- Somewhat, but could improve alignment (1 point).
- No, need to revisit assessment design (0 point).

B7. Am I providing regular feedback to students through various channels (e.g., email, discussion forums, in-person meetings)?

- Yes, I regularly provide constructive feedback to my students (2 points).
 - Somewhat, but could improve frequency and quality of feedback (1 point).
 - No, need to prioritize student feedback (0 point).
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Section C: Open Education (12 points)

C1. Have I done appropriate research and evaluation (e.g., quality, alignment with standards) of the OERs available for the design of my blended learning course?

- Yes, I know what is available and the quality of it (2 points).
- Somewhat, but could improve my knowledge of what exists (1 point).
- No, need to start an adequate research and evaluation of the OERs available (0 point).

C2. Are my OERs well organized, with logical structure and easy-to-follow navigation?

- Yes, my OERs are well organized (2 points).
- Somewhat, but could improve the logical structure (1 point).
- No, need to revisit the organization of the OERs (0 point).

C3. Have I included diverse perspectives, examples, and scenarios to promote inclusivity and cultural sensitivity?

- Yes, my OERs include diverse perspectives for inclusion and cultural sensitivity (2 points).
- Somewhat, but could improve inclusivity and cultural sensitivity (1 point).
- No, need to revisit the perspectives taken (0 point).

C4. Are my OERs robust and accessible on various technological conditions: devices (e.g., computers, tablets, smartphones), browsers, operating systems, internet connection speed)?

- Yes, my OERs are accessible on most technological conditions (2 points).
- Somewhat, but could improve the accessibility or the robustness (1 point).
- No, need to revisit the accessibility and the robustness (0 point).

C5. Have I used clear language, concise headings, and readable font sizes to facilitate understanding?

- Yes, my OERs are clear, concise, and readable (2 points).
- Somewhat, but could improve the OERs to facilitate understanding (1 point).
- No, need to revisit the OERs with facilitation of understanding in mind (0 point).

C6. Have I designed my OERs with reusability in mind, using for instance open formats and licenses that allows others to freely use, modify, and share the OER (e.g., CC BY, CC0), and I gave explicit instruction about how to access, adapt, and share the OER?

- Yes, my OERs only use open formats and licenses (2 points).
- Somewhat, but could verify the openness of the OERs (1 point).
- No, need to revisit my OERs, because contents, formats, or licenses are not open (-10 points).

Section D: Reflection, improvement, and sharing (6 points)

D1. Am I reflecting on the effectiveness of my blended learning design and making adjustments as needed?

- Yes, I regularly reflect on and adapt my blended approach (2 points).
- Somewhat, but could improve reflection frequency (1 point).
- No, need to prioritize reflective practice (0 point).

D2. Are there opportunities for students to provide feedback on their experiences with the blended course?

- Yes, I solicit (or plan time for) student feedback and use it to inform improvements (2 points).
- Somewhat, but could enhance student voice in the design process (1 point).
- No, need to incorporate student perspectives (0 point).

D3. Is the curating work properly organized with my institutional partners so that my OER-only blended learning course can be shared?

- Yes, curation work is organized with the appropriate partners (2 points).
- Somewhat, but could improve the organization of the curating work (1 point).
- No, need to fully organize the curating work by teaming up with the right partners (0 point).

Score (40 points, max).

- **35-40 points.** It indicates a strong OER-only blended learning design, that effectively integrates online and face-to-face instruction and clear instruction to access, adapt, and share the OERs. Consider sharing best practices with colleagues and exploring new technologies to further enhance your blended course.
- **29-34 points.** It suggests areas for improvement, but overall, the OER-only blended learning design is solid. Focus on addressing specific areas for improvement, such as developing more flexible instructional strategies, incorporating student feedback mechanisms, or help users to make reuse of the OERs.
- **Below 29 points.** It may indicate significant challenges or limitations in the OER-only blended learning experience. Prioritize redesigning the blended learning approach or the openness, by revisiting planning, instruction, assessment, reflection, and instruction to reuse, modify and share the OERs.